

**CONCEPT OF ECOSYSTEM. ABOUT THE CONCEPTS OF
“ECOSYSTEM” BY A. TENSLEY AND “BIOGENOCENOSE” BY
V.N.SUKACHEV**

Mamatov Shukurullo Sheramat ugli

Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

PhD researcher

+(998) 94 475 21 02

Abstract: This article analyzes the theoretical and practical foundations of ecosystems and biogeocenoses. The concept of ecosystem was introduced by A.G.Tansley and represents the interaction between living organisms and their environment. VN Sukachev’s concept of biogeocenosis considers these relations adapted to the geographical location. The article discusses energy flow, trophic levels, detritus food chains and key drivers of productivity, as well as the effects of human activities on ecosystems. Examples include rainforests, coral reefs and reforestation initiatives. This article highlights the importance of applying the principles of environmental management and sustainability .

Keywords: ecosystem, biogeocenosis, energy flow, trophic levels, detritus food chain, ecosystem productivity, sustainability, human impact, reforestation, ecological management

Introduction

An ecosystem is a complex network of constantly interacting living organisms and their environment, where biological and physical components constantly interact to maintain balance and functionality. These interactions are not limited to living elements, but also include physical factors such as sunlight, soil, water, and air, which contribute to the overall stability and productivity of the system. The concept of ecosystem was first introduced by A.G.Tansley in 1935 to help researchers understand how organisms interact with their environment. Later, the Russian scientist VN

Sukachev expanded this idea in 1940 and developed the concept of “biogeocenosis”, which broadly covers the interactions between living organisms and their non-living environment in a given area.

This paper provides an in-depth analysis of ecosystems, examining key ecological principles such as biogeocenosis, energy flow, and ecosystem productivity, as well as examining the effects of human activities. Using real-world examples, it analyzes how ecosystems change over time and how these changes can be managed, particularly in terms of increasing agricultural productivity, forestry, and other human activities.

The concept of ecosystem

The term “ecosystem” is used to describe the interactions between organisms and their environment. Ecosystems include “biotic” (living) and “abiotic” (non-living) elements. Biotic components include “autotrophs” (organisms that produce their own food, such as plants and some bacteria) and “heterotrophs” (organisms that consume other organisms, including animals, fungi, and some microorganisms). Abiotic factors such as sunlight, temperature, water and soil affect biological processes in an ecosystem.

Ecosystems work through “energy and nutrient cycling.” Sunlight is absorbed by autotrophs through photosynthesis and is the primary source of energy for this ecosystem. This energy is distributed through “trophic levels,” meaning that energy is transferred from one level to another as organisms eat each other. For example, plants serve as primary producers, herbivores feed on plants, and carnivores eat herbivores. Such interactions support the overall energy flow and nutrient cycling of the ecosystem. We can illustrate this with a real-world example of tropical forests. In tropical forests, the rich biodiversity and constant warm temperatures allow for high levels of primary production. In these ecosystems, plants efficiently absorb solar energy, support a variety of species, and ensure an upward flow of energy across trophic levels.

The concept of biogeocenosis

Sukachev's concept of "biogeocenosis" provides a localized view of ecosystems, showing the interactions between living organisms (flora and fauna) and non-living elements (soil, water and climate) as a whole system within a given area. Although the concept of "ecosystem" is broad, "biogeocenosis" includes interactions between special communities living in geographically specific environments.

So, what is the difference between ecosystem and biogeocenosis? Both concepts describe interconnected systems of life and environment, but Tansley's concept of "ecosystem" is more general and covers global interactions, while Sukachev's concept of "biogeocenosis" refers to special communities in a certain area and their focuses on the relationships between the environment. This distinction is particularly important when studying small ecosystems, such as the "forest biome" or the "river system," influenced by specific environmental factors.

Energy flow and ecosystem productivity

Ecosystem "productivity" is largely determined by energy flow. Plants (autotrophs) convert solar energy into organic matter through photosynthesis, creating the basis of the energy reserve in the ecosystem. The total amount of energy obtained from the environment is called "gross primary production (UBI)", and the energy left over by plants after being used in their respiration is called "net primary production (SBI)", which is the energy that herbivores and available for higher trophic levels.

Only 1-5% of the solar energy reaching the Earth is used for photosynthesis, and the rest is returned and used for other processes such as evaporation. However, even this small percentage is enough to ensure the overall productivity of the ecosystem.

The "10% energy rule" explains that only 10% of the energy is transferred from each trophic level to the next, and the rest is lost as a result of metabolic processes. Therefore, the ecosystem will have fewer predators at the top of the food chain, and the primary producers will have a larger biomass. This situation can be expressed more clearly by the example of coral reefs. Coral reefs are examples of highly productive ecosystems. A mutually beneficial relationship between corals and zooxanthellae (a

type of algae) ensures efficient energy uptake and supports a variety of marine life. In coral reefs, net primary production is high, energy is transferred by the 10% rule, fish and other marine animals feed on algae and small organisms, and predators (such as sharks) are less numerous.

Factors affecting ecosystem productivity

depends on several factors:

Geographical location:

Ecosystems near the equator, such as tropical forests, have high productivity due to constant sunlight and rainfall, while deserts and tundra have low productivity due to harsh environmental conditions.

Seasonal changes:

temperate regions, ecosystem productivity changes with the seasons. Productivity is high in summer when sunlight and temperatures favor plant growth, and low in winter.

Human activity:

Agricultural practices, urbanization, deforestation, and pollution disrupt natural ecosystems, reducing productivity. However, reforestation and sustainable agricultural practices can help restore ecosystems and increase productivity. Reforestation initiatives in Brazil, particularly in the Amazon, have helped restore ecosystems degraded by human intervention. By replanting native tree species and reducing deforestation, these projects have successfully increased ecosystem productivity and biodiversity.

Environmental performance and sustainability

“Ecological persistence” refers to the process by which ecosystems change and evolve over time, resulting in increased complexity and stability. Willpower occurs in two forms:

1. Primary colonization occurs when life colonizes previously dry areas, such as volcanic landscapes.

2. Secondary resilience, ecosystems recover from disturbances such as forest fires or human activities.

As ecosystems evolve, they experience shifts in species composition and structure that help sustain the stability of energy flow and productivity over time. A fire serves as an example of second-order erosion. Following wildfires, “secondary succession” takes place, beginning with resilient pioneer species like grasses and shrubs that help prepare the soil for future growth. Gradually, these initial species give way to a more diverse community of plants and animals, ultimately resulting in a stable forest ecosystem.

Human impacts and ecosystem management

Human activities have profound effects on the health of ecosystems. Deforestation, pollution and climate change are disrupting natural cycles, reducing biodiversity and altering energy flows. However, scientific interventions such as sustainable agricultural practices, reforestation and protected areas can mitigate these impacts. An example of this is sustainable agriculture in Kenya. In Kenya, sustainable agricultural techniques such as crop rotation and organic farming have helped restore soil fertility and increase productivity while maintaining ecosystem balance. This approach increases productivity and ensures the long-term viability of the land.

Human impacts in ecosystem management refer to the effects that human activities have on the natural environment and its ecosystems. These impacts can be both positive and negative, depending on the actions taken and their alignment with sustainable practices. Understanding and managing these impacts are crucial for preserving biodiversity, ecosystem services, and the overall health of the environment. By understanding human impacts, ecosystem management can aim to minimize harm, promote sustainable use of resources, and maintain the balance necessary for ecosystems to thrive.

Trophic levels and detritus food chains

Ecosystems are structured around “trophic levels,” which represent the hierarchical nutritional relationships between organisms. These levels illustrate how

energy is transferred through different groups, such as producers, herbivores, and carnivores. While much attention is often given to herbivorous food chains, where energy flows through herbivores and subsequently to carnivores, another equally vital pathway exists: the “detritus food chain.” This chain focuses on the recycling of energy and nutrients from dead organic matter through the action of decomposers like fungi, bacteria, and detritivores such as earthworms and insects.

The detritus food chain is especially significant in maintaining ecosystem health, as it ensures the efficient breakdown of organic materials. In forest ecosystems, for example, fallen leaves, dead trees, and the remains of animals accumulate over time. These materials are processed by decomposers, which break them down into simpler compounds, releasing essential nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium back into the soil. This process not only enriches the soil but also creates a fertile foundation for the growth of new plants, completing the nutrient cycle.

Furthermore, the detritus food chain contributes to the overall stability of ecosystems by preventing the accumulation of organic waste and maintaining soil structure and fertility. It also supports a diverse community of organisms that rely on decomposed matter for survival, such as fungi, microorganisms, and small invertebrates. These organisms, in turn, serve as food for higher trophic levels, connecting the detritus food chain with the broader ecosystem.

The detritus food chain is a critical component of ecosystem dynamics. By recycling nutrients from dead organic matter, it sustains plant growth, supports biodiversity, and maintains ecological balance, highlighting its essential role alongside the herbivorous food chain in the flow of energy and matter within ecosystems.

Summary

In conclusion, understanding the relationship between living organisms and their environment provides essential insights into the intricate dynamics of ecosystems. Energy flow and nutrient cycling through trophic levels are critical processes that underpin ecosystem productivity. These interactions determine how energy is

transferred from one organism to another and how nutrients are recycled within the system, maintaining ecological balance.

Human activities, such as deforestation, pollution, and overexploitation of resources, as well as natural events like climate change and natural disasters, significantly influence the stability and sustainability of ecosystems. These changes can disrupt energy flow and nutrient cycling, leading to a decline in biodiversity, reduced productivity, and compromised ecosystem health. Recognizing and mitigating these impacts is crucial for preserving the functionality and resilience of natural systems.

A thorough understanding of these dynamics is vital for effective management practices in sectors such as agriculture, forestry, and conservation. In agriculture, for example, sustainable practices like crop rotation, agroforestry, and organic farming can enhance soil fertility and minimize environmental damage. In forestry, responsible logging, reforestation, and habitat restoration can help maintain biodiversity and prevent ecosystem degradation. Conservation efforts, including protected areas, wildlife corridors, and ecological restoration, play a pivotal role in safeguarding ecosystems from further harm.

By applying scientific knowledge and adhering to ecological principles, we can develop strategies to enhance the productivity and sustainability of ecosystems while respecting their natural boundaries. This approach ensures that ecosystems continue to provide essential services, such as clean air, water, and fertile soil, which are fundamental to human well-being. Ultimately, prioritizing the health and balance of our planet's ecosystems is essential for securing the long-term sustainability of Earth's natural resources and ensuring a thriving environment for future generations.

References

1. Begon, M., Townsend, C. R., & Harper, J. L. (2006). Ecology: From individuals to ecosystems. Wiley-Blackwell.
2. Odum, E. P., & Barrett, G. W. (2005). Fundamentals of Ecology (5th ed.). Brooks Cole.
3. Chapin, F. S., Matson, P. A., & Vitousek, P. M. (2011). Principles of Terrestrial Ecosystem Ecology (2nd ed.). Springer.
4. Rockström, J., Steffen, W., Noone, K., Persson, Å., Chapin, F. S., Lambin, E. F., ... & Foley, J. A. (2009). A safe operating space for humanity. *Nature*, 461(7263), 472-475.
5. Foley, J. A., Defries, R., Asner, G. P., Barford, C., Bonan, G., Carpenter, S. R., ... & Snyder, P. K. (2005). Global consequences of land use. *Science*, 309(5734), 570-574.
6. Tilman, D., Cassman, K. G., Matson, P. A., Naylor, R., & Polasky, S. (2002). Agricultural sustainability and intensive production practices. *Nature*, 418(6898), 671-677.
7. Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (2005). *Ecosystems and human well-being: Synthesis*. Island Press.

Internet resources

1. <https://bioprinciples.biosci.gatech.edu/>
2. <http://web.mit.edu/>
3. <https://www.learner.org/>
4. <https://education.nationalgeographic.org/>
5. <https://openstax.org/>